

Long work-hours and job satisfaction: Do over-workers get trapped in bad jobs?

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Key findings

We use the Household, Income and Labour Dynamics in Australia (HILDA) Survey and show:

- Ten per cent of Australians work 50 hours per week or more and report a desire for fewer hours.
- Job-satisfaction amongst these ‘over-workers’ is high, particularly in terms of job security and satisfaction with the work itself.
- Over-workers have higher wages than the population average.
- Over-workers who are dissatisfied with their jobs rarely get trapped—20 per cent of them change jobs within one year and subsequently report improved conditions and satisfaction.
- Only a very small number of dissatisfied over-workers stay in their unsatisfying jobs for more than 2 years
- ‘Trapped’ over-workers tend to have low levels of education. They are most commonly found in farm management and retail and hospitality management.
- Rigid work hours and a reliance on experience make the opportunity cost of job change high, leading to their being trapped.
- The results suggest that improving general human capital can protect workers from being trapped in bad jobs.

What we knew

- There is a modest academic and large popular literature on the topic of long work-hours and their deleterious effect on life satisfaction, work-life balance and psychological health.
- Implicit in this literature is an assumption that workers must dislike their jobs. Drago, Wooden and Black (2009), using HILDA data, found that 23 per cent of Australians worked long hours (50+) and that 10.6 per cent of this 23 per cent identified as “conscripts”—people who would prefer to work less. The authors worried that this might reflect rigid labour markets that trapped people in bad jobs.

What we do

- We use the HILDA panel data to track over-workers over time to observe their occupational decisions, especially around work hours and job change
- We also use a probit model to identify factors that increase and decrease the likelihood that someone is an over-worker

What we know now

- The major determinant of overworking is being a manager (increases the likelihood of over-working by 10 per cent) or a professional (5 per cent).
- Most over-workers are satisfied with their jobs overall, just not with their hours
- Dissatisfied over-workers mostly change jobs or negotiate more satisfactory hours over time.

What this means for policy

- The Australian labour market appears to be sufficiently flexible in terms of allowing workers to adjust work hours.
- If over-work is a problem, the solution lies in cultural change rather than institutional or policy reform.
- Any policies that reduce labour market flexibility are likely to exacerbate problems of over-work or under-work.

Where to now?

- A similar study examining whether the supposed epidemic of under-employment in Australia is similarly a function of people working fewer hours by choice rather than circumstance.
- Breunig, Gong and Leslie (2015) showed that under-work is less prevalent and less persistent than over work.

More information

- Get the full working paper at: https://crawford.anu.edu.au/files/uploads/crawford01_cap_anu_edu_au/2016-02/working_paper_-_fabian_and_breunig_2016_overwork.pdf or the published version at: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/ssqu.12648>
- We would welcome the opportunity to present our research to your team and to discuss potential joint research projects on related or similar topics.
- Contact us at mark.fabian@anu.edu.au or robert.breunig@anu.edu.au

References

- Breunig, R., Gong, X. and Leslie, G. (2015). The dynamics of satisfaction with working hours in Australia: the usefulness of panel data in evaluating the case for policy intervention, *Asia and the Pacific Policy Studies* **2**(1): 130–154.
- Drago, R., Wooden, M. and Black, D. (2009). Long work hours: Volunteers and conscripts, *British Journal of Industrial Relations* **47**(3): 571–600.